

Figure S5: Shared homologs between *Phoxinus phoxinus* and zebrafish, fathead minnow, goldfish, grass carp and common carp.

A. Venn diagram of shared homologs between multiple fish species and the *Phoxinus phoxinus*.
 B. Total number of homologs shared by each species with the *Phoxinus phoxinus*.

A.

B.

